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Machine teaching? Teachers' professional agency in the age of algorithmic tools in education

Tobias Röhl

Centre for Education and Digital Transformation, Zurich University of Teacher Education, Zurich, Switzerland

ABSTRACT

Algorithmic tools promise solutions to educational challenges by automating core teaching tasks. This shift disrupts the traditional role of teachers and the distribution of agency between humans and machines in education. The article explores this shift using a case study on the use of an algorithmic system by teachers in Swiss secondary schools, identifying three key dimensions of agency affected by algorithmic tools: expertise, autonomy, and accountability. Teachers must now justify decisions that deviate from automated systems, defend their professional autonomy against companies offering (seemingly) superior results, and face complexities in accountability, as it becomes distributed across various actors. The shift in teachers' professional agency thus becomes visible as ambiguous and contested, defying notions of a simple replacement of teachers by algorithmic systems.

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Introduction

As in other fields, algorithmic systems¹ promise a technological solution to educational problems. Tasks that are considered central to teaching are increasingly being automated by algorithmic tools: Intelligent tutoring systems provide feedback and select appropriate exercises for individual students (task selection), automated grading systems evaluate essays and open-text exercises (assessment), and learning analytics promise to predict student performance based on their past actions tracked on learning platforms (diagnostics) (for an overview see Luckin et al. 2016; for a critical assessment see Selwyn 2022). This automation of educational tasks not only raises questions about the professional identity of teachers, but also disrupts the established distribution of agency between humans and machines in education.

The introduction of automation in various fields of work and its consequences for workers are a longstanding topic in research on work in the social sciences. Industrial work in particular has been subject to increasing levels of automation by technological developments. A common observation of the 1970s and 1980s was the risk of deskilling of work (Braverman 1974; Wood 1982). Being part of automated chains of production means that

workers need to be less qualified and relegated to menial tasks. They thus become alienated from their work and receive lesser wages. At the same time, more qualified jobs are created that are tasked with supervising automated processes (Hirschhorn 1984). In contrast to industrial work, knowledge work and the work of professions such as lawyers, physicians and teachers has long been considered exempt from the risks of automation. However, with the rise of machine learning tools and other algorithmic systems this has significantly changed (Susskind and Susskind 2017).

Following this line of inquiry, the article investigates how teachers' professional agency is affected by the introduction of algorithmic tools. It thus focusses not on 'learning with technology' but on 'teacher's work with technology' (Selwyn, Nemorin, and Johnson 2017, 390) and thus offers much needed insights into the interplay of professional work and (educational) technologies in schools. First, I will outline the concept of professional agency and its technological transformation in education and other contexts. Building on this, a case study is presented which shows that teachers' professional agency is challenged in terms of their expertise, their autonomy and the accountability of their work. Finally, I will show how this affects teachers' professional agency in a rather ambiguous way. Drawing on the 'social worlds framework' (Clarke and Star 2008), the article reconstructs the technological transformation of professional work not as deterministic processes but as contested shift in which different actors offer competing understandings and trajectories of algorithmic systems.

Professional agency and its technological transformation

Professional agency

Professions can be understood as the 'institutionalization of expertise' in people (Abbott 1991). Professional expertise in turn is usually defined as specialized and formally certified knowledge (Young and Muller 2014; see also Parsons 1939). Building on this rather broad definition with its focus on professional knowledge several features can be added to better grasp professional work. Because they have a highly valued specialized expertise the professions are usually endowed with some degree of autonomy, both as a group and as individual experts (Rueschemeyer 1983). The defining hallmark of a profession is often seen in its 'legitimate, organized autonomy' (71) distinguishing it 'from other occupations in that it has been given the right to control its own work' (Freidson 1988, 71). A sense of autonomy is also important for individual workers to experience their work as meaningful and endowed with sufficient agency (Laaser and Karlsson 2022). At the same time, professionals are seen as serving the public by providing a common good (legal advice, education, health etc.) and are thus held accountable in a very pronounced way (Brodkin 2008; Evetts 2011). This call for accountability of professional work can be at odds with the autonomy, since professionals give up some degree of control over their work to their clients and the broader public (Rueschemeyer 1983). This holds especially true for performance measures that follow a model of 'calculative accountability' (Vriens, Vosselman, and Groß 2018, 1179f.) and abstract from the context specific features of a case that professionals deal with on an individual basis. For teachers in particular, this focus on performance indicators risks neglecting professional judgement and meaningful pedagogy in favour of a façade of performance (Ball 2003).

This interest in professional work is directly linked to questions of agency. If one understands agency as the ‘locus of action, whether in the person, in language, or in some other structure or process’ (Denzin 2004, 82), one can ask for the contribution of different elements to action. Looking specifically at ‘professional agency’ (Eteläpelto et al. 2013) thus means to ask who or what is in control of which actions and hold accountable for these actions. This is especially true when actors are confronted with datafication (Hepp and Görland 2024; for the field of education see, for example, Jarke and Breiter 2020). The line between humans and the technologies and media they employ becomes increasingly blurry and a shift in agency occurs in which neither human actors, nor non-human actors such as technologies and infrastructures are the sole, clearly identifiable ‘locus of action’. Instead, we encounter instances of ‘distributed agency’ (Enfield and Kockelman 2017; Rammert 2008) in which several actors and elements contribute to an action.

Algorithmic systems and professional agency

This notion of distributed agency follows insights from social research on machine learning tools and other algorithmic systems. They are not powerful in and out of themselves but are embedded in a complex of practices, technologies and infrastructures which lend them their power (Beer 2017; Bucher 2018; Crawford 2021). They are thus part of ‘algorithmic cultures’ (Seyfert and Roberge 2016) and, like other technology, are interwoven with human practice (Venturini 2023). Accordingly, algorithmic systems cannot be thought of in isolation from the social circumstances and practices in which they are used (Lange, Lenglet, and Seyfert 2019; Perrotta and Selwyn 2020). In order to be used effectively, they require human control and their areas of use must be selected and prepared accordingly by humans – for example, when the floors and lighting of an airport are adapted so that the systems can better distinguish between luggage, furniture and people (Neyland and Möllers 2017). And the data used to train them needs to be pre-classified and ‘cleaned’ in order to work properly (Pink et al. 2018; Wagenknecht et al. 2024). Consequently, asking for professional agency in the age of algorithmic systems is a question in which one will encounter an entanglement of human and machine agency.

More specifically, algorithmic systems in education have been the subject of research in the field of critical EdTech studies scrutinizing the claims and promises of the industry by making their inherent pedagogies as well as their economic and political agendas visible (Decuyper et al. 2023; Selwyn et al. 2023a; Williamson, Macgilchrist, and Potter 2023). With regard to professional agency, studies in this field of research show how technology intervenes in educational practice not as deterministic force but as something to deal with. As Selwyn, Nemorin, and Johnson (2017) show in an interview study on the digitally mediated work of Australian teachers in two schools, the integration of digital infrastructures in organisational work does not lead to disruptive transformation of the teaching profession. Instead, we find that the introduction of new tools reinforces pre-existing trends that were already in place in the absence of algorithmic systems – such as the increasing need for teachers to account for their performance (Wilkins 2011). Teachers themselves are now increasingly handling digital data reducing education to things that are measurable while neglecting other aspects of teaching and learning such as personal experience and voice (Grant 2022). This raises important questions about teachers’ professional agency at a time when algorithmic systems are proliferating not only in the classroom but also in the staff

room. How do teachers react to the conflicting demands of abstract datafication and engaging with their students (and colleagues) face-to-face?

At the same time, new professions weave their way into schools to adapt to technological changes. ICT coordinators are often teachers who have additional qualifications in the field of digital media and assume new responsibilities in their schools (Geiss and Röhl 2024; Lai and Pratt 2004; León-Jariego, Rodríguez-Miranda, and Pozuelos-Estrada 2020). Entirely new professions are established with data managers handling growing amounts of data in school (Grant 2024; Lewis and Hartong 2022). This, in turn, often leads to conflicts between different professions about what falls under their purview.

Stellwerk – getting students on track

The case presented – ‘Stellwerk’ (literally ‘signal box’) – provides insights into an educational algorithmic system and how it affects teaching as professional work. While Stellwerk is not cutting-edge technology, it is widely used and well-known in the German-speaking parts of Switzerland. Consequently, this is an article about common practices with a commonly used tool in Swiss secondary schools interested in the ‘state of the actual’ rather than the ‘state of the art’ (Selwyn 2008). The developer is not part of ‘Big EdTech’ (Williamson 2022) but a ‘middle tech’ (Bialski 2024) company owned by the canton of St. Gallen. The Lehrmittelverlag St. Gallen is a publisher of textbooks and other teaching materials including Stellwerk – an adaptive system designed to diagnose students’ competences (and possible lack thereof). While its adaptivity is not based on machine learning per se, it is nevertheless an algorithmic system making use of artificial intelligence in a broader sense. Its ability to adapt to the students’ level of expertise builds on ‘item response theory’ (Baker and Seock-Ho 2004) a psychometric paradigm that assigns different probabilities (and thus difficulties) to test items according to data collected in pretests.

Using the example of Stellwerk, I work out how algorithmic systems intervene in school practice and cause shifts in professional agency. Three of the above-mentioned aspects of professional agency are the focus here: autonomy, expertise and accountability. How does an algorithmic system like Stellwerk affect teachers’ professional agency? What does the introduction of such tools mean for teachers’ autonomy and expertise? Who is held accountable when educational practice is partially automated? To answer these questions I follow a case study design (Yin 2013) and use a number of different data: information from the developers’ website, an analysis of the test’s interface, documents and press releases from the authorities, articles from the press, and a news report on Swiss television. The case presented focuses on a specific controversy surrounding Stellwerk, thus embracing ‘anomalies’ (Burawoy 1998) to get insight into the taken-for-granted logic of the test. The data was coded according to principles of Grounded theory (Corbin and Strauss 1990). While the empirical data was approached in an inductive and exploratory fashion, professional agency and its subcategories (autonomy, expertise, and accountability) served as ‘sensitizing concepts’ (Blumer 1954) for the purpose of answering the research questions outlined above.

Stellwerk has been introduced in Swiss lower secondary schools (students aged 13–15) since 2011 and is now widely used in the German-speaking cantons of Switzerland. According to the developers, it enables ‘an assessment of the current status of secondary school students’. It can be used to test ‘skills in the core school subjects of mathematics,

German, French and English' and (since 2023/34) in the scientific subjects of biology, chemistry and physics. On the one hand, the Stellwerk test is a diagnostic tool and can provide 'indications for individual support', while on the other hand it enables a 'social comparison within the year group' (Lehrmittelverlag St. Gallen 2019a). As a 'multidimensional-adaptive test system', Stellwerk also contains adaptive elements and 'adapts to the level of difficulty of the students' (Lehrmittelverlag St. Gallen 2019a). Based on previous entries and answers, they are given tasks of varying difficulty in different areas of a subject. In concrete terms, this means that a student sits in front of the screen and works on tasks from different subjects. For example, a task in German may consist of listening to an audio recording and answering a multiple-choice question. Based on the input, the system determines an initial assessment of competence and gradually assigns tasks with an appropriate level of difficulty. At the end, a graphical overview of the skills in the tested subjects is displayed. It locates the performance of individual students within a standardized scale of 200–800 points. This allows individual performance to be set in relation to a normal distribution and statements to be made about the performance of a test subject in comparison with other students. According to the developers, students should take this test at least once a year in lower secondary school (students aged 13–15), allowing teachers and students to gather longitudinal information about students' competences and areas for improvement.

Adaptive systems such as Stellwerk promise individual support and guidance for learners by adapting teaching material to the learners' performance (Kerres et al. 2023, 2). In times of staff shortages in schools, it is hoped that technical support will nevertheless provide each child with 'their own super teacher' (TA-SWISS 2020, 14; translation by the author). Accordingly, the developers promise teachers relief from 'preparatory and follow-up work' and thus more 'time for consultative discussions' (Lehrmittelverlag 2019b). Such systems thus also supposedly stand for a reform of pedagogical practice in which teachers should act as learning coaches rather than knowledge authorities ('from sage on the stage to guide on the side'; King 1993; Susskind and Susskind 2017, 60).

Standardization and the crisis of academic assessment

One of the advantages of the system mentioned by the developers is its standardization. Stellwerk is a 'standardized test system that is intended to objectively record and compare core school competencies regardless of the type of school attended' (Lehrmittelverlag St. Gallen 2021). This standardization guarantees that Stellwerk represents 'a contribution to the objectification of performance assessment'. Furthermore, the developers' website advertises that the test is aligned with the 'competence-oriented' curriculum 'Lehrplan 21' (Deutschschweizer Erziehungsdirektoren-Konferenz (D-EDK) 2013) valid in the German-speaking Cantons in Switzerland. It therefore not only stands for objectivity, but also for validity, as it contains the state-certified competencies.

The aim is to prepare students for their future in the best possible way. They often take the Stellwerk test in year 8 (around the age of 14). This is the second year of lower secondary school in Switzerland. It is an important point in a student's school career in Switzerland, as this is the first time that students are taught in a differentiated way according to performance – sometimes in different types of schools, sometimes in different classes at the same school or courses in the same class (Meyer 2018, 31–32). This already indicates who will attend a grammar school or undergo vocational training after completing secondary school in year 9. The aim of the Stellwerk test is therefore to 'set the course for the future' and

provide feedback on whether there are any deficits in skills for a grammar school or a specific career, which can then – according to the developers – be worked on. This is also reflected in the name of the test: *Stellwerk* means signal box and thus signifies a place where courses are set, and students are put on their tracks.

Although the *Stellwerk* test was initially only designed as an internal school diagnostic tool to provide teachers and students with a more accurate picture of existing and missing skills, it has recently become a generally recognized assessment tool beyond individual school classes. Many training companies in Switzerland require applicants to submit the results of the school-based *Stellwerk* test. For example, a student reports in the Swiss newspaper ‘20 Minuten’:

You enclose the *Stellwerk* test with your application so that the master teacher can see what you can do. The higher your score, the better your chances of getting the apprenticeship. That’s why the test is so important for us students (20 Minuten 2022b)

The student’s statement highlights the relevance of the test for the young person’s career. The test shows ‘what you can do’ – grades are not given this honour. Accordingly, the *Stellwerk* test serves companies as proof of the suitability of potential trainees. The Department of Education of the Canton of Zurich therefore feels compelled to point out that the:

Stellwerk test [...] is a school support tool. This means that it is not designed to help you find an apprenticeship. Nevertheless, it can happen that a training company also requests this *Stellwerk* profile as a supplement to an apprenticeship application. This is to get a better picture of your academic development... (Bildungsdirektion Kanton Zürich 2024)

The Department of Education is trying to limit the damage here. The assurance that the test ‘is not designed to help you find an apprenticeship’ shows that this is indeed standard practice. The *Stellwerk* test appears here as a further indicator of students’ ‘academic development’. Franziska Peterhans, Central Secretary of the Swiss Federation of Teachers (LCH), is also cautious in a newspaper interview and qualifies the informative value of the test: ‘The *Stellwerk* test is not the same assessment of a pupil as the differentiated school report’ (20 Minuten 2022b). Although the *Stellwerk* test may have a higher degree of standardization, it does not have the same granularity as the assessment of teachers who can assess their students on site.

Despite these objections, companies rely on the informative value of the *Stellwerk* test. They distrust school grades and prefer to rely on the standardized test of a national provider with its promise of objectivity and comparability. School grades appear to be unreliable assessment tools that depend too much on the idiosyncratic assessment practices of individual schools and teachers (Filer 2000; Kalthoff 2013). There is no standardized form of assessment that determines how final grades are arrived at. Teachers use a variety of means in their grading: students’ oral performances, assignments and examination results are usually graded individually, before some form of arithmetic mean is calculated to produce an annual grade for students in a given subject.

Some stakeholders take issues with the idiosyncratic variety of grading. Hans-Ulrich Bigler, director of the Swiss Trade Association from 2008 to 2023, for example, stated in a television interview on national television on 6 July 2011 that a ‘uniform’ assessment system is needed, as there is a ‘proliferation’ of school grades in which grades are no longer

comparable and have lost their meaningfulness (SRF 2011). The *Stellwerk* test appears to be a welcome alternative here and promises comparability beyond the ‘influences of individual schools’, according to a father interviewed in the same program.

This reveals a crisis of academic assessment. Up until the nineteenth century, many schools in German-speaking countries relied on locally limited assessment systems that reflected, for example, rankings in a class (see, for example, the assessment practice of the Jesuit schools in Kalthoff 1998; for England and Wales see Broadfoot 2012, 28ff.). Modern grading systems were an attempt to create comparability through a (seemingly) universal assessment scheme (Lindenhayn 2018). Unlike earlier assessment systems, modern grades promise comparability and follow (at least in theory) a meritocratic ideal allocating people according to their merit alone (Napoletano 2024).

The belief in the reliability of grades achieving this comparability has always been in doubt (Pollard and Filer 2001). The *Stellwerk* test fills a gap here and promises comparability beyond individual teachers and schools. Many social measurement instruments leave their original area of application and enter new areas of application in a ‘parasitic’ (Neyland 2012) manner. This is precisely the case here. A purely diagnostic tool that is ‘only used for support planning’ and from which ‘no grades should be derived’ (Lehrmittelverlag St. Gallen 2019a) has long since become an assessment tool in competition with school grading.

This is in line with a general societal trend away from singular and definitive measures of performance towards a multiplicity of tests in which a number of indicators is used to evaluate individuals (Cardon and John-Mathews 2023) and testing becomes ubiquitous (Marres and Stark 2020). Different sites and actors argue for or against the validity of different tests and their measures. Do we trust the results of a test developed by a company with its claims of objectivity and comparability? Or do we still trust academic grades given by teachers with their promise of in-depth and first-hand knowledge of individual students? This comes down to two different logics and how they are valued by different stakeholders: ‘(a) a behaviourist logic that emphasizes the need and value of standardized testing of curricular knowledge and competencies and (b) an authenticity-centred logic that focuses on creativity, team working, and self-fulfilment’ (Horvath and Steinberg 2023, 571). In terms of professional agency, emphasising the former means to forego the judgement of individual teachers in lieu of standardised data and thus challenging their autonomy as arbiters of academic selection. A ‘trained judgement’ of individual teachers is in certain contexts (such as applying for an apprenticeship) replaced by the ‘mechanical objectivity’ (Daston and Galison 2007) of a standardised test.² While this societal trend towards a ‘trust in numbers’ (Porter 1996) is not new in general and in education in particular (Ball 2003, 2017; Biesta 2015), algorithmic systems lend quantified measurements of performance further credibility by automating calculation and (seemingly) cleansing it further from the stain of human subjectivity.

Vulnerabilities and distributed accountability

For the test to perform its selective function in the sense of an objective measurement, various things must be observed. The developers demand compliance with various rules that are intended to guarantee the most objective measurement possible ‘under the same conditions’ and ‘fairness towards all students’. On their website they state the following:

- Stellwerk may only be carried out in schools under the supervision of a teacher or a supervisor authorized by the school.
- The supervisor ensures that the test conditions are adhered to.
- Students should only use the resources listed in the ‘Resources’ section below.
- During the test, care must be taken to ensure that no other websites are accessed.
- With the exception of technical questions, no help or information is provided by the teacher. (Lehrmittelverlag St. Gallen 2019a)

It turns out that the objectivity promised by the developers is by no means a result of the technical system alone. Instead, teachers are involved and must provide additional services. As in other cases of automation via algorithmic systems there is still work to be done by human actors (Crawford 2021; Neyland and Möllers 2017). The test is objective in the sense of the developers if teachers ensure that the students are kept away from other elements such as websites and prohibited ‘aids’ like dictionaries in language lessons. Teachers themselves are only envisaged as ‘supervisors’ who may offer technical assistance at most. This limits their professional agency, at least during the times when the Stellwerk test is administered but does not fundamentally distinguish this school-based examination from other forms of written examination.

It is precisely because the Stellwerk test is so relevant in German-speaking Switzerland that cheating attempts can and will occur. In the summer of 2022, there was an incident that left the developers and education policy stakeholders in the cantons in need of an explanation and attracted media attention (20 min 2022a). Students at a secondary school in Butikon (canton of Schwyz) discovered a weakness in the system:

The trick is very simple. All you have to do is press the Control, Shift and C keys at the same time and the source code appears. In the source code, you can then see the solution with one click. (20 Minuten 2022b)

With a little computer knowledge, individual students were able to find a loophole and view the source code of the web platform that runs the Stellwerk test. The source code then contains the respective solutions to the tasks. Students who discovered this first informed their classmates about this possibility *via* WhatsApp. The scam was uncovered because there were many questions that were answered correctly without exception, which made the teachers at the school suspicious:

We didn’t do it quite so cleverly. If we hadn’t typed in the correct answer to all the questions and got the highest score, we wouldn’t have been caught. (20 Minuten 2022b)

This already indicates that the expertise of the knowledgeable teacher on site is still in demand. Accordingly, there is a further shift when it comes to questions about who takes responsibility for a result or even a perceived failure to achieve it. Shortly after the weakness in the system became known, the Department of Education of the Canton of St. Gallen, which owns the Lehrmittelverlag St. Gallen and thus is jointly responsible for the Stellwerk test and its administration, attempted to appease the situation:

The fact that the source code can be displayed in the browser of the website in order to examine page components is a common tool in web development. As a test provider, the Lehrmittelverlag St. Gallen reacted immediately in collaboration with the application

provider Arcadix, localized the vulnerability and fixed it. The analyses show that the students did not actively hack the system, but exploited a vulnerability in the application. [...] The site assessments generate results that are collected over the entire school year and can be verified. Outliers can thus be recognized. Teachers are encouraged to report suspicious test results to the Office for Primary Education. (Bildungsdepartement des Kantons St. Gallen 2022)

First, the students' trick is downplayed as a 'common tool'. Accordingly, from the point of view of the Department of Education, what the students did was not active 'hacking', but rather the exploitation of a 'vulnerability'. This means that the students are not malicious computer specialists, but merely beneficiaries of a security vulnerability that has been marked as common and therefore exploitable. It is made clear that test providers and software developers 'reacted immediately' and took remedial action. These two stakeholders thus assume responsibility in a double sense. They identify themselves as responsible actors and, through their repair measures, are the ones who rectify the damage themselves. At the same time, the Department of Education is practising damage limitation. The attempts at cheating are only part of a test series and can therefore be recognized as a deviation. This in turn means that teachers are obliged to report 'suspicious test results'. They are the ones who have to recognize and report anomalies.

This reveals a peculiar distribution of accountability (Röhl 2022). The use of an algorithmic system means that ownership and responsibility can no longer be clearly attributed, but must be seen in the context of the actors involved (Reddy, Cakici, and Ballestero 2019). On the one hand, it is the providers and developers who have a duty to rectify errors in the application. On the other hand, however, teachers are still called upon to take responsibility for their students' attempts to cheat. So instead of ensuring clarity and consolidation, the introduction of a standardized and universally used system also complicates the question of the accountability of assessments and errors.

Discussion and conclusion: contested shifts

What does the case of Stellwerk tell us about professional agency in the age of algorithmic systems? The case study presented here does not point in the direction of an inevitable deskilling and substitution of the teaching profession by algorithmic tools. Despite all automation narratives, the effectiveness of algorithmic systems can only ever be understood in interaction with the human actors who use them. An adaptive system such as the Stellwerk test is integrated into a wide range of school and extracurricular assessment practices: from school diagnosis and support to the selection of trainees. This reveals multiple shifts in professional agency. Algorithmic systems encroach on the autonomy of the profession and challenge the legitimacy of established school selection procedures. They add new indicators to the range of school assessments and make it necessary to interpret them in the context of other diagnostics. In other words, teachers' grades are not replaced, but an additional level must be considered and new areas of expertise are required from teachers. Finally, teachers are still held accountable, even if algorithmic systems appear to replace their assessment. They must ensure that students do not use prohibited tools or exploit technical loopholes in the system. Consequently, automation always requires some kind of supporting practices (Crawford 2021; for education see Selwyn et al. 2023b).

The case of the Stellwerk test thus points to the rather ambiguous nature of automation and its effect on professional agency. On the one hand, algorithmic systems such as Stellwerk

challenge the autonomy and expertise of professionals by aiming to replace human judgments with seemingly objective measurements. Teachers and their representatives, on the other hand, contest this view and ask for a re-evaluation of their work. According to this sentiment, teachers' expertise is needed more than before in order to counter the risks of algorithmic systems. This resembles developments in other fields that have been subject to automation. Aircraft automation, for example, will require even more qualified pilots to monitor the automated systems and respond appropriately in the event of a malfunction – and this in spite of opposite claims of the developers of 'fly-by-wire' technologies in the early 1980s (Hancke 2020). Some researchers thus argue that professional work always needs to involve sophisticated forms of epistemic work confronted with an increasingly complex work environment (Nerland and Hasu 2021). In education, similar tensions between automation and professional agency have been identified with the recent onslaught of machine learning tools in the classroom (Selwyn et al. 2023a). In any case, the introduction of new technologies in the workplace does not determine professional practice but shifts and redistributes agency (Hepp and Görland 2024).

These shifts and redistributions in professional agency cannot be attributed to a technological change alone but follow pre-existing developments. Pedagogies and technologies coincide – those who call for more efficiency and measurability in pedagogical practice are proponents of tools that promise just that (Selwyn, Nemorin, and Johnson 2017). Automation in education is thus not a neutral technical process but an educational endeavour in which different pedagogical ideas compete with each other (Decuyper et al. 2023). Accordingly, Neil Selwyn (2024) identified different positions and groups of proponents and critics surrounding algorithmic systems in education: While, for example, 'social proponents' emphasize the ability to address the needs of different learners, 'corporate proponents' are keen to make education more efficient. 'Social critics', on the other hand, warn of the risks of standardisation and the constraints that technology places on educational practice. In terms of professional agency, this means that notions of efficiency and professional autonomy are often pitted against each other when tools promise to automate educational tasks.

Ideas of automating education are older than the recent influx of algorithmic systems. Earlier attempts to automate pedagogical tasks and technically optimise learning can, for example, be found in B.F. Skinner's 'teaching machines' introduced in the United States in the 1950s (Watters 2021), but also in European countries like Sweden starting around the same time (Rensfeldt and Rahm 2023). Here too, one can find similar tensions between teachers' professional agency and automation.

The introduction of technical systems in the classroom always interacts with existing endeavours to steer education in a certain direction. Following the 'social worlds framework' (Clarke and Star 2008) I understand this as contested process between different groups of actors with divergent perspectives and interests. The technological transformation of schools is therefore not a deterministic development, but itself part of negotiations about what education should achieve (Macgilchrist, Allert, and Bruch 2020). These contested shifts in professional agency consequently also point to the possibility of governing the path of automation in education differently. There are different ways in which algorithmic systems can be integrated into teachers' professional work. As a result, educational and political actors have much more influence on how machine learning and other algorithmic systems are used in schools and classrooms than common narratives about the inevitability of technological change often suggest (Selwyn et al. 2020; Sidorkin 2024).

To what extent and in which areas teaching will be automated by which algorithmic systems should be left open to public debate. Things can always be otherwise.

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Notes

1. The terms ‘algorithmic system’ or ‘algorithmic tools’ are used here to refer to the wide range of applications that use some form of algorithmic automation, whether driven by machine learning or based on artificial intelligence more broadly defined.
2. Albeit the literature is full of examples of ‘algorithmic bias’ and other problems with the supposed objectivity of algorithmic systems reinforcing, for example, racist and sexist stereotypes (Aker et al. 2021; Mullaney et al. 2020; Noble 2018).

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ORCID

Tobias Röhl <http://orcid.org/0000-0003-1363-6633>

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